

GÖTTINGER MISZELLEN ZUR UGARITISTIK

Herausgegeben von Reinhard Müller, Clemens Steinberger und Noah Kröll

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- Author:** Andrew Burlingame
Wheaton College
drew.burlingame@wheaton.edu
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- Abstract:** This article proposes toponymic identifications for several entries appearing in RIH 83/47', first published in 2019. The new insights resulting from this study include an identification of the first alphabetic attestation of the toponym Paṭaratu (previously attested only in logosyllabic texts and in one alphabetic text as a gentilic), a second attestation of the previously *hapax* toponym ʿry, a series of arguments in favor of identifying the entries appearing in this text as uniformly toponymic, and a number of topographic observations intended to contribute to the challenging work of locating these settlements within the kingdom of Ugarit.
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Toponymic Remarks to RIH 83/47⁺ (RIH II, no. 43)

Andrew Burlingame

1. Introduction

The text under consideration, RIH 83/47⁺, was discovered during the 1983 season of excavations at the site of Ras Ibn Hani, and was first published in 2019 (Bordreuil and Pardee 2019, 115–117). As the fragments from which this tablet was reconstituted were found at Locus XXIX of the North Palace at Ras Ibn Hani, the text belongs to Lagarce’s “Groupe 4” and can be dated, along with most of the texts recovered from the North Palace, to the reign of ‘Ammitamru III (see Lagarce *apud* Bordreuil, Pardee, and Roche-Hawley 2019, 14, 18).¹

In his “Catalogue raisonné des textes de Ras Ibn Hani 1977-2002,” Pardee classified the text among other “Textes économiques” and, more specifically, among “Relevés de comptes” (Pardee 2019, 32). The introductory formula of the text is unusual, and this together with the structure and organization of the text merit further study, but the focus of the present study is strictly toponymic. The editors identify the opening four lines as a summary of silver owed by ‘Ammuyānu (215 shekels). The remainder of the text is treated as a list of “creditors,” i.e., the individual contributors to whom repayment is due.

As the editors observe, most of these creditors are actually the names of settlements within the kingdom, but they correctly note that several of the entries could be interpreted as either toponyms (TNs) or personal names (PNs), a fact introducing a measure of uncertainty into the interpretation of the text. In this brief article, I suggest that all of the entries can now be recognized as toponyms based on two varieties of evidence.

First, some of the names in this text treated as ambiguous in the edition can now be more clearly identified with attested toponyms. Second, in one case of clear ambiguity, an independently observable trend in Ugaritian administrative practice can be invoked to achieve resolution. Before introducing the specific entries at issue, I reproduce the text in its entirety as presented in the *editio princeps* (RIH II, no. 43; a proposed revision is offered at the conclusion of this study).

RIH 83/47⁺ = RIH II, no. 43

Recto

¹ tgmr . k[s]p ¹	Total d’argent
² d ‘ly . w d [‘]l ¹	qui est passé en compte débiteur, à savoir au [débi]t
³ ‘myn . ḥm[š]t ¹	de ‘Ammuyānu : deux cent
⁴ ‘šrt . k ¹ bd ¹ mītm	quinze (sicles).
⁵ ‘r . ḥmšm	(De la ville de) ‘Aru : cinquante (sicles) ;

¹ Note that Lagarce refers to this king as ‘Ammitamru II, reflecting the traditional enumeration of Ugaritian kings found in works like Yon 1997 / 2006 and Singer 1999. The numbering employed here follows the revised system proposed in Arnaud 1999.

⁶ ḥrlm . ḥmšt	(de) ḤRLM : cinq (sicles) ;
⁷ kttǧlm . ḥmšt	(de l'individu) KTTǧLM : quinze (sicles) ;
⁸ ʕšrt	
⁹ ʕry . ḥmšt	(de) ʕRY : quinze (sicles) ;
¹⁰ ʕšrt	
¹¹ ṭmry . ʕšrt	(de la ville de) Ṭamrāya : dix (sicles) ;
¹² pṭrt . ʕšrt	(de) PṬRT : dix (sicles) ;
<i>Tranche inférieure</i>	
¹³ ypr . ʕšrt	(de) YPR : dix (sicles) ;
<i>Verso</i>	
¹⁴ mšbt . ḥmšt	(de la ville de) Mašibatu : cinq (sicles) ;
¹⁵ mādḥ . ḥmšt	(de la ville de) Maʿaduḥu ² : cinq (sicles) ;
¹⁶ mril ¹ . ḥmšt	(de la ville de) Maraʿilu : cinq (sicles) ;
¹⁷ ḥlb špn . ḥmšt	(de la ville de) Ḥalbušapuni : cinq (sicles) ;
¹⁸ šbn . ʕšrt	(de la ville de) Šubbanu : dix (sicles) ;
¹⁹ uškn . ḥmšm	(de la ville de) ʿUškanu : cinquante (sicles) ;
²⁰ [.] ṛcʿšrm	[(de ...)] : [v]ingt (sicles) ;
²¹ [. ḥ]mšt	[(de ...)] : [c]inq (sicles).

2. Toponymic and Topographic Discussion

The editors identified most of these entries as well-known toponyms, as indicated by their introduction of the parenthetical clarification, “(de la ville de).” They judiciously³ observed, however, that several entries were strictly ambiguous and could perhaps be identified as either personal names or toponyms. The entries {ḥrlm} in l. 6, {kttǧlm} in l. 7, {ʕry} in l. 9, {ṭmry} in l. 11, {pṭrt} in l. 12, {ypr} in l. 13, and {uškn} in l. 19 were all regarded as potentially problematic (2019, 117). Of these, the editors treated {kttǧlm} in l. 7 as a personal name (adding “(de l’individu)” in their translation) and provisionally preferred to understand {ṭmry} in l. 11 and {uškn} in l. 19 as toponyms (though noting

² The edition has “Maʿadiḥu,” but it is clear from the remark on p. 117 that Maʿaduḥu was intended.

³ Cases of personal names that were identical to toponyms were already known, but the editors’ identification of the first clear evidence for the personal name uškn, found in RIH 83/17:27¹ (= RIH II, no. 9), demonstrated that even greater caution was required than most would have previously thought necessary (see Bordreuil and Pardee 2019, 62, 117). Prior to the discovery of this evidence, no interpreter would have hesitated to identify an instance of {uškn} in an alphabetic Ugaritic text with the prominent settlement of that name located in the southern coastal plain of the kingdom, but the new textual evidence from Ras Ibn Hani demonstrated beyond doubt that even such apparently obvious identifications could turn out to be misleading.

that both could also be personal names). The other four entries were deemed ambiguous and were left without an indication of their status (“ville” vs. “individu”) in the published translation (see above).

The entry {ḫrlm} in l. 6 is (to my knowledge) unique, as the editors state.⁴ The remaining entries, however, can now be shown to have parallels elsewhere that may serve to clarify the function of the text as a whole.

The entry {kttg̃lm} in l. 7 can be identified as a toponym discussed in van Soldt’s *The Topography of the City-State of Ugarit* (2005, 27) and is found in two other alphabetic texts (RS 17.392:2 [= KTU¹⁻² 4.310; KTU³ 3.18] and RS 19.105:25–26 [= KTU¹⁻³ 4.643]).⁵ Unfortunately, neither of these texts allows us to locate this settlement, and van Soldt (2005, 112) does not assign it to any of his groups of towns.

The entry {ry} (l. 9)⁶ was not included among toponyms gathered and studied in van Soldt 2005, as its first published attestation had not yet appeared. But a more recently published text, RS 94.2614 (= RSO XVIII, no. 2; KTU³ 4.820), provides an attestation of this graphic sequence in a context that makes its toponymic status virtually certain. The text in question consists of a list of town names followed by numerals, which, based on a note written on the reverse of the tablet in logosyllabic cuneiform, refer to quantities of animal hides. The list of settlements is arranged in two columns. All TNs appearing in the left-hand column are independently attested and belong to van Soldt’s Groups 6–8 (i.e., southern

⁴ Moreover, as this text was first published in 2019, the lexeme ḫrlm does not appear in the dictionary of del Olmo Lete and Sanmartín, the most recent edition of which was published in 2015.

⁵ The first of these attestations, appearing in RS 17.392, is potentially ambiguous, as it refers to *nsk kttg̃lm*, “the founder(s) of *kttg̃lm*.” The same text mentions *nsk arym* (ll. 5–6) and *nsk art* (l. 8). The latter of these clearly involves a TN (“founder(s) of ²Arutu”), but the former involves a gentilic (“founder(s) of the men of ²Aru”). In other words, the case could be made for interpreting *kttg̃lm* either as a TN (like *art* in l. 8) or as a plural term referring to a group of individuals, comparable to the toponymically defined group *arym* in l. 6. Virolleaud seems to have had the latter possibility in mind when he suggested in his *editio princeps* of RS 17.392 (1957, 170) that *kttg̃lm* might represent “un mot composé au pl.” like *mdrg̃lm* and *hdg̃lm* (both terms referring to professional groups and incorporating the Hurrian morpheme *soḫ(e)li* [-*uhli*], used to form Hurrian *nomina actoris* [see Wegner 2007, 57–58]). Such a classification was suggested more explicitly by Friedrich (1961, 36: “ugar. Berufsbezeichnung”), Aistleitner (1963, 160: “Bez. e. Berufs?”), and Dietrich and Loretz (1966, 199–200).

The discovery of RS 19.105 (= KTU 4.643) in 1955 (published in 1965) shed new and clearer light on the question, as the form {kttg̃lm} appeared following the preposition *b* “in” in l. 26 of the text and, by emendation, in the preceding line as well ({kt-t>g̃lm}), in a context in which the resulting prepositional phrase could only be understood to indicate the town in which the individuals named at the beginning of each of these lines were to be found. Virolleaud (1965, 142) described the text as a “[l]iste de gens habitant diverses villes,” suggesting a toponymic status for *kttg̃lm*, and he listed this term in the index of “villes et pays” (1965, 166). Gordon (1965 / 1998, 425 [sec. 19.1336]) drew on this new text and interpretation in producing his glossary entry for *kttg̃lm*, where it is treated as a place name (though without discussion). This new understanding of the term was quickly accepted by others, who noted that it was in fact preferable for RS 17.392 on internal grounds as well, as both *arym* and *art* pertained to towns of origin (Dietrich, Loretz, and Sanmartín 1973, 110; Pardee 1974, 280 n. 26).

While some continued to hold that a term referring to a professional group (typically “bowmakers” is assumed) provided the etymology of the term (e.g., Astour 1977, 129; 1981b, 14 with n. 16; Sanmartín 1995, 180–181; Watson 2001, 117), its toponymic value was generally accepted (exceptions include Laroche 1980, 139 [citing Dietrich and Loretz 1966, though these authors no longer held to the position outlined there, as noted above] and Heltzer 1982, 89 with n. 34 [rejecting the position outlined by Lipiński in an editorial note appearing in Heltzer 1979, 478–488 n. 224; he does not, however, address the clear indications of the toponymic value of the term that Lipiński’s editorial remark had identified]) and remains normative today (see Belmonte Marín 2001, 165 and del Olmo Lete and Sanmartín 2015, 468).

⁶ Bordreuil may originally have read this entry as {ky} (see his remarks *apud* Bordreuil et al. 1984, 427; Bordreuil and Pardee 2019, 116 with n. 130; see further Cunchillos 1989, 357 n. 30). While the second sign of this sequence shows some damage in the published photograph, the editors indicate that the reading {ry} is certain (Bordreuil and Pardee 2019, 116).

groups). Independently attested toponyms in the right-hand column belong to his Groups 1N, 1S, 1, and 2 (i.e., northern groups) (see van Soldt 2005, 111–114; Bordreuil and Pardee 2012, 18). Among these settlements in the right-hand column appears a new toponym, {ʿry} (RS 94.2614 ii 10). If the organization of these settlement names is consistent, then the town of ʿry is likely to be sought at the northern frontier of the kingdom (a possibility the present text may support, as discussed below).

The entries {pṛrt} in l. 12 and {ypr} in l. 13 can be identified as the towns of Paṛaratu and Yaparū.⁷ The former of these is significant, comprising the first alphabetic attestation of this TN, as previous attestations were limited to logosyllabic texts and one instance of an alphabetic gentilic (*pṛrt*).⁸ Furthermore, the immediate juxtaposition of these two TNs in the present list aligns with their cooccurrence elsewhere and tends to support van Soldt’s placement of Paṛaratu in his Group 4 (see van Soldt 2005, 90 n. 93, 113 with n. 188).

If these identifications are correct, then {ḫrlm} is the only unique and uncertain term (unless it represents an error, to be corrected to {ḫr-bḡ-lm}, a poorly attested town name [see van Soldt 2005, 22, and further below]), and in this light, the editors’ preference to treat {ṫmry} and {ūškn} as toponyms is surely justified. Independently observable trends in Ugaritian administration, however, provide a second reason to prefer the toponymic interpretation of {ūškn} in this text. Specifically, the fact that the largest quantities of silver registered in the list are associated with ʾAru (50 shekels, l. 5) and ʾUškanu (50 shekels, l. 19) conforms precisely to evidence for the comparable size and importance of these two towns available among the administrative texts from Ras Shamra.⁹

In light of these observations, RIH 83/47¹ can be understood to record quantities of silver that had been provided by a number of the kingdom’s settlements (aligning—even if only approximately—with Saadé’s [2011, 444] inclusion of this text among “listes toponymiques”). The text does not provide any hint as to the purpose these contributions served, and this point of ambiguity is further complicated by both the unusual expression *d ʿly* found in the introduction (and remarked by the editors [Bordreuil and Pardee 2019, 117]) and the fact that the total recorded in the introductory paragraph, 215 shekels, does not agree with the total arrived at by adding up the individual entries, namely, 220 shekels (also noted by the editors [2019, 117]).¹⁰ What appears certain, however, is that the contributors in this record were towns rather than individuals. These are presented here together with their respective contributions as well as the group number assigned to each in van Soldt’s study.

⁷ For Paṛaratu, see van Soldt 2005, 38; for additional bibliography, see Belmonte Marín 2001, 219 and del Olmo Lete and Sanmartín 2015, 677 (*pṛrt*). For Yaparū, see van Soldt 2005, 25–26; for additional bibliography, see Belmonte Marín 2001, 341 and del Olmo Lete and Sanmartín 2015, 960.

⁸ See references in preceding footnote for lists of attestations.

⁹ These data are presented and examined in van Soldt (2005, ch. 5) and suggest that ʾAru and ʾUškanu represented the towns of greatest administrative significance—and possibly size—in the southern plain (van Soldt 2005, 127). Further discussion and bibliography can be found in Burlingame forthcoming.

¹⁰ One of the anonymous peer reviewers makes the clever observation that the final entry in the list may have comprised an unanticipated/last-minute addition to the list. In other words, the total of 215 was written down first, followed by the entries occupying lines 5–20, which do reach the stated total. The final entry of 5 shekels may then have been added after the fact. Though impossible to prove, this is imaginable and would account for the discrepancy.

Line	Settlement	Contribution	Group (van Soldt 2005)
5	ʾAru	50	8
6	ḤRLM	5	[not treated in van Soldt 2005]
7–8	KṬṬĠLM	15	?
9–10	ʿRY	15	[not treated in van Soldt 2005]
11	Ṭamrāya	10	1N
12	Paṭaratu	10	4?
13	Yaparu	10	4
14	Maṣibatu	5	2a
15	Maʾaduḥu	5	2a
16	Maraʾilu	5	2
17	Ḥalbu-Ṣapuni	5	2
18	Šubbanu	10	6
19	ʾUškānu	50	6
20	[...]	20	[not preserved]
21	[...]	5	[not preserved]

This presentation illustrates that, to the extent determinable, TNs appear together with other members of the same group in this list (that is, the groups are not interspersed as they are in some lists). As noted already, the fact that Paṭaratu and Yaparu appear together agrees with their treatment elsewhere and supports van Soldt’s placement of Paṭaratu in Group 4 (van Soldt 2005, 90 n. 93, 113 with n. 188).

Regrettably, the three entries of uncertain location (*ḥrlm*, *kṭṭġlm*, and *ʿry*) appear together between ʾAru (Group 8) and Ṭamrāya (Group 1N). Since *ʿry* appears in the right-hand column of RS 94.2614, which otherwise seems to include only northern settlements (as discussed above), its placement here immediately prior to Ṭamrāya may allow us to hypothesize a location among the towns of van Soldt’s Group 1.

This leaves the entries in ll. 6–8, which can only be addressed in the most speculative of terms. As noted already, *kṭṭġlm* cannot presently be placed with any certainty. The etymology of the toponym is unclear (see n. 5, above), but the final three consonants (*-ġlm*) have been the subject of debate within studies dedicated to Ugaritic toponymy. Two settlements located in the vicinity of Ugarit’s northern frontier with Mukiš exhibit a final element conventionally normalized as *-ḥuliwe*, namely, Bītu-ḥuliwe and Ḥarbu-ḥuliwe. The final syllable of the former is spelled with both PI (read by van Soldt, among others, as *we*) and BI (read *bē*); the latter TN is attested only with the second of these spellings (see van Soldt 2005, 15, 22). Van Soldt (2005, 15 n. 88) follows Kühne (1974, 166–167) in regarding both TNs as Hurrianized (through the addition of the Hurrian morpheme *≈ve/≈we*¹¹). He notes the further, though less certain, possibility that the TN represented in syllabic cuneiform as URU *ḥar-ba-ḥu-li-bé* (RS 17.062*:15' [= PRU IV, p. 66]) may be identical to the alphabetically written TN *ḥrbġlm* (van Soldt 2005, 22 with n. 155), a possibility first raised tentatively by Nougayrol (1970, 146), then, more explicitly by Dietrich, Loretz, and Sanmartín (1973, 110 with n. 1), and subsequently accepted by others (e.g.,

¹¹ For this genitive morpheme and case inflection in Hurrian, see Giorgieri 1999; Wegner 2007, 65–66; Campbell 2015, 15–16.

Heltzer 1976, 10; 1979, 487–488 n. 224; Astour 1981a, 9 n. 53; 1981b, 14; 1995, 67 n. 86; cf. Kühne 1974, 167 n. 73; for further relevant bibliography, see del Olmo Lete and Sanmartín 2015, 398).

If this equivalence is correct, then *kṭṭḡlm* may represent a similarly formed TN, and, given the placement of Bītu-ḥuliwe and Ḥarbu-ḥuliwe in Group 1N, perhaps *kṭṭḡlm* may be similarly located. This is admittedly speculative, resting entirely on a presumption that the existence of two similarly formed TNs on the northern frontier of the kingdom provides *prima facie* grounds for situating a third TN of the same sort in the same region, which need not be the case. It would, however, align with the likely northern placement of ʿry and Ṭamrāya, which follow it immediately in the text under discussion.

Turning to *ḥrlm*, methodological prudence requires that we leave the placement of this TN open for the moment. Nevertheless, I register here (with due caution) that, should this represent a simple error for an intended *ḥr<bḡ>lm*, then this TN would (if it is in fact the alphabetic counterpart to syllabic Ḥarbu-ḥuliwe [see above]) represent another entry in this section of RIH 83/47^r belonging to van Soldt’s Group 1N, located at the northern frontier of the kingdom.

These new toponymic identifications facilitate the uniform treatment of the contributors listed: all are best understood as the names of towns within the territory of the kingdom of Ugarit. Their arrangement in this list, however, is no clearer today than previously. The list begins with ʾAru, located at the southern end of the kingdom (see Burlingame forthcoming for detailed discussion), moves to three towns of uncertain location, but possibly to be situated together with Ṭamrāya on Ugarit’s northern frontier, moves next to towns in Group 4, just north of the city of Ugarit itself, then to Group 2a/2 at the northwest corner of the kingdom, and closes with entries from Group 6, occupying the southern coastal plain east/southeast of Lattakia. It is to be hoped that further work on the recently published administrative documents from Ras Ibn Hani will permit a clearer understanding of this text and its organization, but in the meantime, the entries treated here can be safely added to the growing body of evidence for the toponymy and topography of the kingdom of Ugarit.

3. A Revised Translation

To close this study, I offer here a revised presentation of the text with translation. I provisionally follow the editors’ understanding of the opening section appearing in lines 1–4 though, as noted above, the unusual wording found here precludes certainty.

RIH 83/47^r = RIH II, no. 43

Obverse

¹ tgmr . k[s]ṫp ¹	Total amount of silver that has
² d ʿly . w d [ʿ]ṫ ¹	“gone up” (is registered as owed?), and that is to the debit
³ ʿmyn . ḥm[š]ṫ ¹	of ʿAmmuyānu: two hundred
⁴ ʿšrt . kṫbd ¹ mṫtm	and fifteen (shekels).
<hr/>	
⁵ ʾr . ḥmšm	(From the city of) ʾAru: fifty (shekels);
<hr/>	
⁶ ḥrlm . ḥmšt	(From the city of) ḤRLM: five (shekels);
<hr/>	
⁷ kṭṭḡlm . ḥmšt	(From the city of) KṬṬḠLM: fifteen (shekels);
⁸ ʿšrt	

⁹ ʿry . ḥmšt	(From the city of) ʿRY: fifteen (shekels);
¹⁰ ʿšrt	
<hr/>	
¹¹ ṭmry . ʿšrt	(From the city of) Ṭamrāya: ten (shekels);
<hr/>	
¹² pṭrt . ʿšrt	(From the city of) Paṭaratu: ten (shekels);
<hr/>	
<i>Lower edge</i>	
<hr/>	
¹³ ypr . ʿšrt	(From the city of) Yaparū: ten (shekels);
<hr/>	
<i>Reverse</i>	
¹⁴ mšbt . ḥmšt	(From the city of) Mašibatu: five (shekels);
<hr/>	
¹⁵ mādh . ḥmšt	(From the city of) Maʿaduḥu: five (shekels);
<hr/>	
¹⁶ mril ^l . ḥmšt	(From the city of) Maraʿilu: five (shekels);
<hr/>	
¹⁷ ḥlb špn . ḥmšt	(From the city of) Ḥalbušapuni: five (shekels);
<hr/>	
¹⁸ šbn . ʿšrt	(From the city of) Šubbanu: ten (shekels);
<hr/>	
¹⁹ uškn . ḥmšm	(From the city of) ʿUškanu: fifty (shekels);
<hr/>	
²⁰ [.] ṛʿšrm	[(From the city of) ...]: [t]wenty (shekels);
<hr/>	
²¹ [. ḥ]mšt	[(From the city of) ...]: [f]ive (shekels).
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Bibliography

Abbreviations

The abbreviations generally follow RIA (Streck, Michael P., et al., eds. 1928–2016. *Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie*. Berlin etc.: De Gruyter) and EUPT (<https://eupt.uni-goettingen.de/>). Additional and deviating abbreviations:

PRU IV = Nougayrol 1956.

RIH II = Bordreuil, Pardee, and Roche-Hawley 2019.

RSO XVIII = Bordreuil and Pardee, with Hawley 2012.

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